

Prevalence of Sino-Nasal Abnormalities and Associated Socio-Demographic Factors in South West Region of Satpuda Range: A Hospital Based Cross Sectional Study

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Abstract:

Background: Given the significance of the burden of sino-nasal abnormalities faced by inhabitants of the south west region of Satpuda Range, our study sought to ascertain the prevalence of these abnormalities and the related socio-demographic factors in the region.

Material and Method: In this hospital-based cross-sectional study, patients who reported to the outpatient department of ENT at CIMS Medical College and Hospital in Chhindwara, MP, India, with a complaint of craniofacial discomfort between February 2022 and January 2024 were included. A comprehensive history and ENT examination were conducted to identify the sino-nasal source of craniofacial discomfort. The chosen cases had computed tomographic (CT) scans of the sinuses and preliminary diagnostic nasal endoscopy. An association was shown between age, gender, smoking status, and history of trauma and the occurrence of craniofacial discomfort caused by sino-nasal pathology.

Results: Among a group of 200 patients experiencing craniofacial discomfort, 130 of them had a sino-nasal malfunction. Among the 100 patients, 80 were male and 50 were female. A mean age of 34.859±4.846 years was recorded among the research participants. The most prevalent sino-nasal pathology seen in these individuals was deviated nasal septum (DNS), followed by nasal polyps and chronic sinusitis. Application of binary logistic regression revealed an association between smoking and history of trauma with the existence of sino-nasal cause among patients with craniofacial complaints.

Conclusion: Sino-nasal anomalies were a primary factor contributing to craniofacial discomfort in patients seeking treatment at the ENT outpatient department. Particular focus should be given to individuals who engage in cigarette smoking and those with a reported history of facial trauma.

Keywords: Craniofacial pains; Sino-nasal; Socio-demographic factors.

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Introduction

The international standards define craniofacial pain as a heterogeneous term including a wide range of painful disorders affecting the head and face. [1] Previous research has examined distinct primary and secondary factors contributing to craniofacial discomfort, encompassing both central and peripheral sources. [2] It is necessary to address pain resulting from both of these sources individually, based on the specific reason. While the epidemiology of the primary causes of facial pain remains uncertain, it is well-established that chronic idiopathic facial pain is a prevalent and challenging issue that places a substantial burden

on the healthcare system. [3,4] Nasal/paranasal causes of craniofacial aches include acute rhinitis, chronic rhinitis, nasal polyps, nasal septum deviation, turbinate hypertrophy, contact point headache, nasal fracture, nasal papilloma, nasopharyngeal cancer, and boil nose. [4,5] The precise mechanism by which sino-nasal abnormalities cause craniofacial discomfort is complicated and uncertain. Several hypotheses have been proposed, such as the negative pressure resulting in the Hoover headache and facial pain, compression of the anterior ethmoidal nerve causing craniofacial pain symptoms, and the neuro-

peptide theory attributing the pain to substance P and other neuro-peptide proteins. [6] Stammberger and Wolfe postulated that persistent inflammation of the sinus lining is a significant factor contributing to headaches inside the sino-nasal pathway. Regardless of the underlying reason, these aches continue to be the primary cause of misery and a compromised quality of life for the affected persons. [7,8]

The objective of this study was to investigate the prevalence of sino-nasal causes and related socio-demographic characteristics among patients at the ENT out-patient department (OPD) of a tertiary care hospital in the south west area of Satpuda range who report with headaches.

Aim and Objectives

The objective of the present study was to ascertain the frequency of sino-nasal anomalies and analyze the related socio-demographic parameters in the south west region of the Satpuda range.

Material and Method

The present cross-sectional research was carried out in the ENT department of CIMS Medical College and Hospital, situated in Chhindwara, MP, India, throughout the period of February 2022 to January 2024. The study received ethical approval [Ref. No. CIMS/EC/2022/625], from the Institutional Ethical committee of the hospital, where it was conceptualized and carried out.

Sample Size Calculation: The sample size was determined using the World Health Organization (WHO) Sample Size Calculator, which used a previous study to obtain the numbers specific to the algorithm employed by the WHO calculator. [9] A non-probability consecutive sampling method was employed to choose the sample for the purpose of research.

Inclusion Criteria: The research included all patients aged 18 to 65 who had craniofacial pains, following provision of written informed consent from them.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients present with pre-existing neurological disorders, such as migraine, cluster headache, or brain tumour, or with persistent pain resulting from ophthalmologic or ENT disorders. Patients who were pregnant or have not provided consent to participate in this study

were additionally excluded as well during the first phase.

Methodology

All patients had comprehensive history extraction and examination of their rhinology, neurology, and ophthalmology. The neurologic and ophthalmologic evaluation involved regular inspection of the patients to identify any ocular or neurological factors contributing to headaches and to exclude them from the trial during the first phase. The otolaryngological examinations consisted of computed tomographic (CT) scans of the sinuses and first diagnostic nasal endoscopy. The patients involved in the research underwent administration of the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) to evaluate the intensity of pain. Data on socio-demographic factors were inputted into a proforma specifically created for this research. A comprehensive history was acquired concerning the event and its effects on the sino-nasal area. In addition, the research participants were explicitly queried about their tobacco smoking habits. Participants who smoked regularly were categorized as smokers in the research.

Statistical Analysis:

All statistical analysis was conducted using the Statistics Package for Social Sciences version 23.0. Frequencies and percentages computed for qualitative variable data. Statistical analysis was employed to characterize the risk variables and the distribution of individuals afflicted with sino-nasal causes. Patients were classified based on the distinct groups of sino-nasal causes and non-sinonasal causes. A study using binary logistic regression was conducted to assess risk variables associated with the occurrence of sino-nasal causes. Statistical significance was established for differences between groups when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Results

Among the 200 individuals involved in the research, 130 had conclusive sino-nasal pathology, verified either physical examination or appropriate radiographic testing. A mean age of 34.859 ± 4.846 years was recorded among the research participants. The most frequent pathology among sino-nasal causes was a deviated nasal septum, followed by nasal polyps and chronic sinusitis. [Table 1]

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of the study patients and types of sino-nasal anomalies (n=200)

Variables	Mean±SD	Range (min-max)	N (%)
Age (years)	34.859 ± 4.846	15-65	-
Average duration (Years)	2.501 ± 1.499	0.4-12	-
Gender	Male	-	135 (67.5)
	Female	-	65 (32.5)
Type of sino-nasal anomaly	DNS	-	51 (25.5)

	Nasal Polyps	-	-	32 (16)
	Chronic Sinusitis	-	-	29 (14.5)
	Others	-	-	18 (9)

Applications of binary logistic regression revealed a significant correlation between smoking and history of trauma with the existence of a sino-nasal abnormality in patients with craniofacial symptoms. [Table 2]

Table 2: The correlated factors relating to the presence of sino-nasal causes

Variables	P-value
Age (reference is <35 years)	0.4979 (NS)
Gender (reference is male)	0.4849 (NS)
Smoking (reference is non-smokers)	0.0000 (S)
History of trauma (reference is no history of trauma)	0.0169 (S)

NS- Not Significant, S- Significant

Discussion:

Common symptoms encountered by general physicians, neurologists, neurosurgeons, ENT specialists, and psychiatrists in their clinics include headaches and craniofacial pains. The association between craniofacial discomfort and Sino-nasal anomalies has been shown in several investigations conducted in different regions of the world. [10-12] By employing standard examination techniques and pertinent investigations, we discovered that 65% of our participants exhibited the occurrence of sino-nasal pains among the individuals suffering from headaches, congruent with previous research findings. [13,14] These may be attributed to the physical consequences of the structural defect, the accompanying inflammation, and the chronic nature of the condition. Evidence from both local and foreign sources has confirmed the occurrence of craniofacial discomfort or headache in individuals with nasal/paranasal anomalies. [15,16]

Our investigation also uncovers a significant proportion of individuals experiencing sino-nasal reasons who were not identified by general doctors or neurologists. These findings indicate that the individuals involved in the study had endured prolonged periods of intense pain and impairment. Patients, albeit incurring the expenses and experiencing the adverse effects of the medicine, did not see any significant improvement, in the alleviation of their craniofacial discomfort.

Therefore, it is crucial to promptly identify the sino-nasal factors and provide patients with conclusive surgical treatment to reduce their pain and impairment and enhance their overall quality of life. Anatomical factors leading to nasal/paranasal anomalies might contribute to headaches or craniofacial discomfort. Typically, these individuals initially consult with general doctors or neurologists. The patient may have significant discomfort in the head and facial area due to nasal obstruction and pressure effects. [17,18] In addition to structural abnormalities, the presence of fluid or pus accumulation, reduced air entry, and prolonged ineffective medical therapy can all contribute to the

patient's susceptibility to chronic craniofacial discomfort. [17] The presence of headache or chronic pain problems significantly impacts the patient's general quality of life and can also lead to non-compliance with medical treatment, which can have severe consequences for the patient. Hence, it is imperative to promptly manage pain in order to enhance the global quality of life for patients with chronic craniofacial discomfort originating from the nose or paranasal region. [19,20] Typically, these aches do not improve with conventional therapy and patients need to be carefully assessed for surgical intervention. Delays in referring patients to the ENT department and a lack of knowledge about the underlying reasons among general physicians and other specialist doctors may hinder the timely and effective treatment of these patients experiencing persistent headaches. A number of previous researches have determined that a history of trauma is linked to the occurrence of sino-nasal anomalies. [21] The results in our study are comparable to those previously reported. Anatomical abnormalities in the nasal area resulting from trauma can lead to the perception of pain and discomfort. DNS, including the nasal spur, was the most frequent source of persistent craniofacial discomfort originating from the nasal/paranasal region in our experimental design, followed by nasal polyps. Furthermore, it is consistent with current literature. [22] Furthermore, it is important to note that DNS is a frequently occurring abnormality and is routinely performed in ENT surgeries.

Hence, if a patient is experiencing persistent pain and their general practitioner promptly identifies the issue and refers the patient to a specialized medical institution, the patient may potentially experience less suffering. No statistically significant correlation was found between age and gender and chronic pain in our investigation. Males constituted the majority of our patients. A smaller female population and a limited age range may explain the absence of correlation. There was a significant correlation between smoking and the occurrence of sino-nasal infection in individuals

with craniofacial symptoms. In the smoking population, chronic rhinosinusitis is a prevalent abnormality.

Limitation of study:

One significant constraint of our study was its lack of prospective nature, which prevents us from concluding that headache or craniofacial discomfort is a result of abnormalities in the nose or paranasal sinuses. Both the sample size and the use of self-administered questionnaires provide methodological challenges. As this study was not conducted on a population, the conclusions cannot be generalized. In lieu of a random sample of all patients with craniofacial pains from different hospitals in the region, a particular cohort of patients in a tertiary care hospital was selected for the study.

Furthermore, the study design did not include surgery or post-treatment follow-up to establish the conclusive connection between Sino nasal abnormality and severe headache.

In future investigations on the topic, we recommend conducting work on a larger and more representative sample size utilising locally created and standardized psychometric instruments.

Conclusion

Sino-nasal anomalies were a primary factor contributing to craniofacial discomfort in patients seeking treatment at the ENT OPD. Particular focus should be given to individuals who engage in cigarette smoking and those with a personal history of facial trauma.

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